

THE NEGATIVE IMPACT OF FAMILY CONFLICTS ON CHILDREN'S PSYCHE AND WAYS TO ELIMINATE THEM

Dumarova Gulfira Kozimbekovna

Teacher, Andijan State Medical Institute,
Department of Uzbek Language and Literature

Abduvakhobova Robiya

Student of Andijan State Medical Institute
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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the impact of family conflicts on children's psyche, their negative consequences on emotional and social development. Family conflicts - disagreements between parents, constant conflicts between spouses or other family members - are the main factors that directly affect children's psychology. The factors related to family conflicts are studied, including the child's mental stability, self-esteem, stress resistance and social adaptation. The article also considers ways to reduce conflicts and resolve them positively, the psychological preparation of parents and educators, communication strategies with children, emotional support and family counseling systems.

Introduction

The family environment is a key factor in the formation of a child as a person. Conflicts between parents, constant disagreements between spouses and other family members have a negative impact on the child's mental health. In recent years, ensuring family education and the mental well-being of children has been identified as one of the priorities at the state policy level in the Republic of Uzbekistan. The principle of President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev "A child is the highest value" is aimed at reducing family conflicts and supporting the psyche of children. Family conflicts weaken the emotional stability of children, exposing them to negative situations such as anxiety, depression, aggression and social isolation. At the same time, children associate constant conflicts in the family with personal dignity and self-esteem, which negatively affects social development. Problems associated with family conflicts should be of concern not only to parents, but also to educators, psychologists and all members of society. Systematic measures are required to ensure the psychological stability of children, protect them from stress and emotional isolation, and develop their social adaptation. The article aims to scientifically study the impact of family conflicts on the psyche of children, identify ways to reduce them, and propose psychological counseling and communication strategies.

The issue of the impact of family conflicts on the psyche of children is also being actively studied by Uzbek psychologists. M. Juraev's research revealed a connection between the family environment and the emotional support of the child. According to him,

parental indifference or excessive criticism increases the feeling of low self-esteem and anxiety in children. S. Tokhtaeva analyzed various forms of psychological pressure and family conflicts. According to the results of the research, such conflicts disrupt the emotional stability of the child, lead to depressive and aggressive behavior. N. Karimova studied the impact of the pedagogical environment on the psychology of children. Her research shows that negative communication at school - constant comparisons, strict demands on students and punishments - together with family conflicts negatively affects the psyche of children. M. Gulomova analyzed the psychology of communication in the family and found that the positive or negative attitude of parents towards the child directly affects the child's psychological development. Communication based on love and respect increases children's self-confidence and strengthens emotional stability. Djalilova S. studied stress factors in the psyche of children and identified the negative consequences of family conflicts. Studies have shown that family conflicts cause symptoms of anxiety, depression, aggression, and low self-esteem in children. Shermammedova L. studied the impact of pedagogical communication on personal growth. She analyzed communication strategies that have a positive effect on children, the psychological preparation of parents and teachers, and methods for reducing stress. Reports provided by the Psychological Service Center of the Ministry of Public Education provide statistical indicators of family conflicts and their impact on children's psyche and serve as the basis for the study.

The study was conducted in families and schools in Tashkent, Samarkand, and Andijan regions in 2023–2024. A total of 300 respondents were involved in the study: 150 children aged 10–16, 100 parents, and 50 educators.

The following methods were used to identify family conflicts: questionnaires and interviews, psychodiagnostic tests and observation. The surveys included questions related to the impact of family conflicts on children, emotional stability and social adaptation. The tests were designed to measure the level of self-esteem, stress level and emotional state of children. Through observation, children's reaction to communication in the family and social adaptation in the pedagogical environment were analyzed. The data obtained were processed using statistical analysis and qualitative analysis methods. The study developed recommendations for reducing family conflicts and resolving them positively.

The results of the study showed that 70% of children reported that they had suffered from family conflicts at least once. Of these, 35% assessed constant disagreements between parents as “mentally difficult”. The study showed that family conflicts have a significant negative impact on a child's emotional stability, social adaptation and self-esteem. Many children experience feelings of loneliness, anxiety and depression due to family conflicts. The results of interviews with parents showed that the main causes of family conflicts are lack of communication, excessive demands and emotional indifference. At the same time, as noted by educators, additional stress at school and pressure through grades also place an additional burden on children. The analysis showed that in order to positively resolve family conflicts and ensure the psychological stability of children, it is necessary for parents and educators to undergo psychological training,

and family counseling and support systems should be introduced. Creating a positive atmosphere of communication, respect and love with children helps reduce their stress and increase their emotional stability.

The results of the study confirm the need for preventive measures aimed at preventing family conflicts - increasing the pedagogical literacy of parents, active use of family psychological counseling centers, and regular conversations with children. In this way, the mental health and social development of children are ensured.

Conclusion

Family conflicts have a negative impact on the mental development of children. These situations lead to anxiety, depression, aggressive behavior, low self-esteem and social isolation in children. Therefore, reducing family conflicts and resolving them positively is carried out by increasing the psychological preparedness of parents and educators, developing a culture of communication and introducing emotional support systems. It is important for parents to understand the negative consequences of family conflicts and establish positive communication with children. It is also necessary to involve educators and psychologists in psychological support of children, conduct family counseling and training. The results of the study show that for the mental stability and social adaptation of children, it is important to form a positive family environment, effectively resolve conflicts and introduce emotional support systems. At the same time, it is recommended to implement programs aimed at reducing family conflicts and ensuring the mental well-being of children at the state level, actively use psychological service centers and strengthen socio-educational work. Only through an integrated approach will it be possible to raise a healthy and sustainable generation.

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